

The regulatory landscape of macrophage interferon signaling in inflammation

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The pervasive role of the innate immune system is established by interferons. Emerging research shows an underappreciated ability of macrophages to regulate and propagate interferon responses in infectious and autoinflammatory disease states. In this review, we will discuss recent findings demonstrating the immunomodulating effects of macrophage interferon signaling. Apart from provoking cellular antimicrobial defenses, interferons augment the inflammatory activity of macrophages. These immunologic adaptations place the macrophage in the center of the interferon system and at the forefront of immunity. Consequently, macrophages are implicated in the pathogenesis of interferon-driven autoinflammatory disorders, such as SLE. In these disease states, the recognition of immunogenic ligands triggers macrophages to adopt an inflammatory phenotype through interferon signaling. This will amplify immune responses, eventually leading to autoinflammation. A better understanding of the macrophage's role in interferon signaling will support the future elucidation of novel targets amenable for clinical treatment. (*J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2023;152:326-37.)

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Interferons (IFNs) underlie the competence of the innate immune system to ward off pathogens. In viral infections, IFNs are secreted to induce an antiviral state in host cells, supporting our first line of defense against pathogens.¹ Moreover, IFNs recruit leukocytes to the site of infection and augment their activity.² These measures ultimately aim to interfere with viral replication and dissemination, curtailing the infection. Perturbed IFN responses may therefore underlie severity and susceptibility to viral infections.³ Predictably, impaired IFN responses are a

Abbreviations used

ADAR1:	Adenosine deaminase acting on RNA 1
cGAS:	Cyclic GMP-AMP synthase
dsDNA:	Double-stranded DNA
dsRNA:	Double-stranded RNA
ERV:	Endogenous retrovirus
IC:	Immune complex
IFN:	Interferon
IRF:	Interferon regulatory factor
ISG:	Interferon-stimulated gene
ISRE:	Interferon-stimulated response element
JAK:	Janus kinase
MDA5:	Melanoma differentiation-associated gene 5
PAMP:	Pathogen-associated molecular pattern
PRR:	Pattern recognition receptor
RIG-I:	Retinoic acid-inducible gene 1
SAMHD1:	Sterile alpha motif HD domain 1
ssRNA:	Single-stranded RNA
STAT1:	Signal transducer and activator of transcription 1
STAT2:	Signal transducer and activator of transcription 2
TLR:	Toll-like receptor

hallmark of severe COVID-19 manifestation.^{4,5} More than half a century of research since their discovery, the role of IFNs is now known to extend well beyond antiviral responses. Namely, IFNs orchestrate various distinct homeostatic processes and immune responses to maintain physiological integrity.^{6,7} Accordingly, disconcerted IFN responses have long been implicated to drive various autoinflammatory disorders, such as SLE and Aicardi-Goutières syndrome. In addition, IFNs commonly contribute to local or systemic inflammation as seen in rheumatoid arthritis and macrophage activation syndrome. Because perturbed IFN signaling appears as a common denominator in these conditions, they are now widely recognized as so-called interferonopathies. The pervasive role of IFNs necessitates investigative efforts into all facets of the IFN system to infer clinically relevant targets to reduce the burden of inflammatory disease.

The IFN system is directed toward interfering with microbial dissemination, principally by enhancing interferon-stimulated gene (ISG) expression. On infection, nearly any host cell will produce IFNs as an intrinsic response against microbes, but also to protect neighboring cells and activate leukocytes. Purposely, some leukocytes are competent producers of IFNs themselves and highly responsive to the regulatory effects of IFNs, forming a feed-forward loop. The capacity of leukocytes to produce IFNs is dependent on cell lineage and cellular microenvironment, like the presence of pathogens and cytokines. Classically, there are lineages of cells specialized in the secretion of specific types of IFNs. For instance, plasmacytoid dendritic cells are accepted to

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be the predominant producers of type I and type III IFNs, whereas T cells are the foremost type II IFN-secreting leukocytes.⁸⁻¹¹ However, various other IFN-producing leukocytes have been identified, including macrophages,¹²⁻¹⁵ thereby challenging the current dogma of the lone IFN producers.

The dual nature of macrophages, being both tissue-resident and derived from migratory monocytes, facilitates their universal role in tissue homeostasis and immunity.¹⁶ Importantly, macrophages are effective mediators of immunity by taking on the role of judge, jury, and executioner in innate immune responses. Pathogen recognition receptors (PRRs) constitute a wide number of sensors macrophages use to judge environmental exposures, such as pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). The main PRRs to consider for IFN responses are transmembrane receptors such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs) and cytosolic receptors such as retinoic acid-inducible gene 1 (RIG-I) and melanoma differentiation-associated gene 5 (MDA5). Macrophages use their repertoire of PRRs and mediators to discriminate between intracellular versus extracellular pathogens, viral versus bacterial, and endogenous versus exogenous exposures, effectively enabling macrophages to execute an appropriate set of actions in response to their environment, including the propagation of an IFN response. Apart from secreting IFNs, macrophages are responsive to IFNs, placing them in the center of the IFN system.^{1,12} Yet, this central role also implicates macrophages in interferonopathies.^{17,18} Transcriptional profiling using state-of-the-art technological advancements has allowed for the characterization of processes steering the IFN system, shedding light on delicate regulatory cascades. This review will cover the current understanding of regulatory networks underlying IFN responses in macrophages.

FUNCTIONAL HALLMARKS OF IFNs IN MACROPHAGES

An integral feature of IFNs is their ability to enhance cellular responsiveness to immunologic challenges. These effects were first observed more than 50 years ago and are yet to be fully elucidated.¹⁹ Since then, the IFN system is established to comprise 3 classes of cytokines: type I, II, and III IFNs. There are several subclasses of type I (including IFN- α subtypes and IFN- β) and III IFNs (IFN- λ 1 to 4), and a single type II IFN (IFN- γ). The evolutionary advantage of these subclasses is largely unknown, but functional differences come down to receptor affinity.^{20,21} Despite shared nomenclature, the different types of IFNs share little structural homology.²²⁻²⁴ Accordingly, each class of IFNs binds a different receptor, canonically eliciting distinct signaling cascades. Their commonality is their regulatory role, exerting immunomodulating effects either autocrine or paracrine (Fig 1).

Biochemically, the binding of type I IFNs to IFN- α/β receptor 1 and 2 triggers conformational change, allowing tyrosine kinase 2 and Janus kinase (JAK) 1 to phosphorylate signal transducer and activator of transcription 1 (STAT1) and 2 (STAT2), causing heterodimerization. STAT1/STAT2 recruits IFN regulatory factor 9 (IRF9) to assemble heterotrimeric transcription complex IFN-stimulated gene factor 3 (ISGF3). Distinctly, type II IFN binds IFN- γ receptor 1 and 2, leading to JAK1- and JAK2-mediated phosphorylation and homodimerization of STAT1. The newly formed transcription complex IFN- γ activation factor will canonically translocate to the

nucleus to bind gamma-activated sequence promoter elements, whereas ISGF3 binds IFN-stimulated response elements (ISREs), both promoting the expression of ISGs. Type III IFNs bind a heterodimeric receptor of IFN- λ receptor 1 and IL-10 receptor beta subunit, yet share their downstream signaling pathway with type I IFNs (Fig 1).

ISGs are located downstream of ISREs, mainly encoding proteins with antimicrobial properties to protect the host from pathogenic exposures. Some of the most well-characterized ISGs are oligoadenylate synthetases, IFN-induced proteins with tetratricopeptide repeats, and IFN-induced GTP-binding protein. Strikingly, IRFs are also ISGs, thus generating a positive feedback loop in the transcription of ISGs. Similarly, various PRRs are under the control of ISREs. Altogether ISGs work in concert, targeting all stages of the viral life-cycle, from entry to egress.²⁵ ISGs are extensively studied in viral infections, but given how studying IFNs in nonviral immunity is relatively novel, little is known about the antibacterial properties of ISGs. It is likely for ISGs to eradicate bacterial pathogens in a similar way to viral infections, by limiting conserved aspects of replication and migration.²⁶⁻²⁹ Importantly, IFNs contribute to monocyte mobilization by stimulating the secretion of chemokines, including C-C motif ligand 5 and C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 10.^{30,31} Similarly, IFNs serve as upstream determinants of inflammatory responses, mediating the inflammatory IL-12 response of monocytes.³ IL-12 is a potent inflammatory cytokine requiring negative regulation by the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10.³² Interestingly, IL-10 secretion is regulated by an autocrine and paracrine type I IFN loop. On sensing LPS (a bacterial cell wall component), macrophages will unleash an inflammatory response, including the secretion of IFNs. The type I IFNs sequentially upregulate the macrophage's ability to produce IL-10, thereby resolving bacterial inflammation.^{33,34} These findings suggest type I IFNs to form a regulatory circuit able to reprogram macrophages to promote both inflammation and resolution.

Despite the ability of type II IFN to induce antiviral responses, it is a notorious activator of macrophages by enhancing the expression of macrophage signature genes containing gamma-activated sequence promoter elements in their promoters or enhancers (Fig 1). Perhaps the most well-established effect of type II IFN is the enhancement of antigen presentation through MHC-II, enabling macrophages to recruit the adaptive arm of immunity.³⁵ Similarly, type II IFN supports the clearance of microbials by boosting core immunologic properties of the macrophage, such as phagocytosis and secretion of inflammatory cytokines, nitric oxide, and reactive oxygen species.³⁶ The significance of type II IFN to the macrophage's phenotype is demonstrated by its ability to differentiate monocytes to inflammatory macrophages, even in absence of M-CSF.³⁷ Thereby, the type I and II IFN pathways are distinct. Still, type I and II IFN signaling have been shown to overlap. These effects are partially explained by the ability of type I IFNs to also form STAT1 homodimers, and type II IFN to signal via ISGF3,³⁸⁻⁴⁰ effectively enabling IFNs to tread into the pathways of other types of IFNs, causing substantial overlap in the cellular response to different types of IFNs. These effects are especially apparent in macrophages lacking STAT2 or IRF9, disabling the formation of ISGF3.⁴¹ When the ISGF3 complex is disrupted, macrophages show a gene expression signature more commonly associated with type II IFN stimulation. As to type III IFNs, first discovered in 2003, they form the most recent addition to the IFN system.^{42,43} Investigative efforts are directed

FIG 1. IFNs modulate macrophage responsiveness. IFNs modulate a broad spectrum of fundamental phenotypical characteristics of the macrophage. Apart from managing inflammatory responses, homeostatic processes regulated by macrophages require IFN signaling. Noncanonical signaling allows distinct IFNs to signal through common pathways in macrophages. *IFNAR1*, IFN alpha and beta receptor subunit 1; *IFNAR2*, IFN alpha and beta receptor subunit 2; *IFNGR1*, IFN- γ receptor 1; *IFNGR2*, IFN- γ receptor 2; *IFNLR1*, IFN- λ receptor 1; *IL10R2*, IL-10 receptor beta subunit; *GAF*, IFN- γ activation factor; *GAS*, gamma-activated sequence; *NO*, nitric oxide; *ROS*, reactive oxygen species; *STAT*, signal transducer and activator of transcription; *TYK2*, tyrosine kinase 2.

toward understanding the additive value of type III IFNs over a more rudimentary IFN system featuring only type I and type II IFNs. Current leads suggest a local tissue-specific and first-responder role of type III IFNs, whereas type I IFNs induce a strong systemic immune response.^{42,44-48} Combined with the individual kinetics of IFN subtypes, these findings may account for the biological relevance of the immune system to have various types and subtypes of IFNs at its disposal.²¹

An obstacle to studying IFN signatures is the potency of IFNs. Minute quantities of type I IFN, below the detection threshold of common assays, can have a significant influence on IFN signatures.⁴⁹ This phenomenon is well illustrated by IFN signaling under homeostatic conditions, which is facilitated by low-level type I IFN secretion. One of the main roles of IFNs, in absence of environmental challenges, is to prime immune cells.⁵⁰ For instance, macrophages show microbiota-driven priming by IFN, offering protection against subsequent viral infection.^{51,52} This is indirectly supported by the fact that germfree mice show increased susceptibility to infections.⁵¹⁻⁵⁴ Also, in IFN-reporter mice, it was shown that immunologically active tissues, such as the spleen, lymph nodes, and bone marrow, actively partake in IFN signaling in the absence of environmental challenges.⁵⁵ Basal IFN signaling was most strongly observed in monocytes, and this priming effect was shown to be critical to their antiviral responsiveness *in vivo*. Besides immunologic responses, myeloid-lineage cells mediate tissue homeostasis. The IFN pathway is pivotal to osteoclast differentiation and homeostasis, where IFNs mainly serve as negative feedback signals to the expression of transcription factors involved in osteoclastogenesis.⁶ This homeostatic role of IFN is supported by mice lacking either type I or type II IFNs, because they show reduced bone

density.^{56,57} Of particular interest, reduced bone density is strongly associated with inflammatory diseases, such as SLE and rheumatoid arthritis^{58,59}; IFN signaling is therefore possibly adding to this pathogenic role of macrophages.

TRIGGERING MACROPHAGES TO PRODUCE IFNs

More than 65 years ago, mammalian cells were first characterized to possess the inherent ability to produce IFNs, in response to viral exposures.⁶⁰ Moving forward, a plethora of types, roles, and producers of IFNs have been discovered.^{42,43} Today, the macrophage's ability to produce IFNs is receiving increasingly more attention. Interestingly, macrophages produce IFNs in divergent inflammatory conditions, ranging from viral and bacterial exposures to endogenous ligands (Fig 2). Classically, viral nucleic acids are the principal ligands causing macrophages to produce IFNs. To cater to this recognition process, macrophages feature a broad range of nucleic acid sensors, including RIG-I/MDA5, cyclic GMP-AMP synthase (cGAS), TLR3, TLR7, TLR8, and TLR9.⁶¹ Double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) transcripts are detected by cytosolic MDA-5/RIG-I, either directly when presented as dsRNA or following its conversion from double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) to dsRNA by RNA polymerase III.⁶² Alternatively, MDA-5/RIG-I may also recognize single-stranded RNA (ssRNA). Activated MDA-5/RIG-I will engage the mitochondrial antiviral signaling adaptor to recruit TANK-binding kinase 1. TANK-binding kinase 1 serves as a central kinase in the IFN pathway, responsible for the dimerization and translocation of IRF3, IRF5, and IRF7. Arrived in the nucleus, IRF3 binds ISREs to act as a transcriptional activator of type I IFNs. Quite similar to the MDA-5/RIG-I pathway, cGAS recruits TANK-binding kinase

FIG 2. IFN-inducing pathways in macrophages. A broad range of microbial and endogenous molecular patterns is recognized by pattern recognition receptors found on the membrane and inside of the macrophage. For example, transmembrane receptor TLR4 predominantly recognizes LPSs derived from Gram-negative bacteria, signaling through TRAF3. In contrast, cytosolic nucleic acid receptor cGAS mainly binds viral DNA, signaling through STING. Despite featuring distinct upstream signaling pathways, IFN responses are induced by central signaling kinase TBK1 mediating the translocation of key transcription factors IRF3, IRF5, and IRF7 to the nucleus. On binding ISRE sites in the genome, these transcription factors mediate the transcription of genes encoding for IFNs. *cGAMP*, Cyclic guanosine monophosphate-adenosine monophosphate; *GTP*, guanosine-5'-triphosphate; *MAVS*, mitochondrial antiviral signaling; *MDA-5*, melanoma differentiation-associated gene 5; *RNA pol III*, RNA polymerase III; *STING*, stimulator of interferon genes; *TBK1*, TANK-binding kinase 1; *TRAF*, activate TNF receptor-associated factors.

1 through stimulator of IFN genes, leading to IRF3, IRF5, and IRF7 activation. The main dissimilarity between these pathways is their ligand, because cGAS is inherently more responsive to dsDNA as opposed to the preferred binding of dsRNA by MDA-5/RIG-I.⁶³ These cytosolic sensors are the first signaling cascades to become activated in macrophages, on viral exposures such as the herpes simplex virus.⁶⁴ Alternatively, macrophages actively sample their environment using endosomes, contributing to the recognition of pathogens. These endosomes harbor nucleic acid sensors TLR3 (dsRNA), TLR7 (ssRNA), TLR8 (ssRNA), and TLR9 (DNA with CpG motifs) able to activate TNF receptor-associated factors to signal for IFNs through IRF3, IRF5, and IRF7.⁶⁵⁻⁶⁸ Apart from inducing IFNs, many of these signaling pathways branch off to initiate complementary inflammatory responses via, for example, nuclear factor- κ B, to synergistically drive the inflammatory phenotype observed in activated macrophages.^{61,69-71} In recent years, the involvement of TLR2 and TLR4, responsive to bacteria, viral proteins, and lipoproteins, has been implicated in macrophage-mediated type I IFN responses.⁷²⁻⁷⁶ This is of particular interest because it supports the broad relevance of IFN responses outside of viral infections.

To this day, the ability to secrete type II IFN is largely regarded to be restricted to T cells and natural killer cells. Yet, an increasing number of reports suggest macrophages to produce multiple IFNs

in response to infections and cytokines.⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰ Thus far, the ability of macrophages to produce type II IFN has predominantly been described in the lungs but is likely to extend to other organs and conditions. Because the lungs are a primary site for pathogen exposure, they feature extensive immune activity and macrophage diversity, mediated by IFNs.⁸¹ Most alveolar macrophage populations display anti-inflammatory activity after an infection, which is associated with the ability of type I IFNs to mediate resolution.²⁹ In contrast, lung interstitial macrophages may acquire an antigen-presenting phenotype, associated with type II IFN exposure.^{35,82} Similar to T cells and natural killer cells, macrophages appear responsive to IL-12 and IL-18 costimulation, leading to type II IFN secretion.¹³ Given the notable presence of IL-12 and IL-18 in lung tissue, the interstitial macrophage phenotype might partially be induced through the secretion of type II IFN by macrophages.^{83,84} Notably, type III IFNs are the most abundantly produced IFNs by alveolar macrophages during influenza infection.⁸⁵ Similarly, TNF and type II IFN-primed monocyte-derived macrophages produce both type I and III IFNs following rhinovirus stimulation, whereas IL-4-primed monocyte-derived macrophages do not.¹⁵ Here, only the IFN-producing macrophages were found to curtail the viral infection. These findings correspond with the impaired ability of patients with asthma to clear viral infections, where macrophages display diminished type III IFN production.⁴⁴ Interestingly, it also displays

heterogeneity in macrophage phenotypes, because the ability to produce IFNs is not ubiquitous among all macrophage subtypes.

Collectively, macrophages produce IFNs in response to a broad repertoire of environmental exposures, whether it be viral or bacterial. Given their sentinel-like role, macrophages are among the highest-expressing cells in regard to PRRs. Although T cells and plasmacytoid dendritic cells might be more potent IFN producers once activated, the macrophages in our first line of defense may have to depend on their own IFN production.¹³ Combined with the prominent ability of macrophages to seek out and scavenge immunogenic ligands, this makes macrophages critical producers of IFN.

ENDOGENOUS CONTROL OF IFNs IN MACROPHAGES

An extensive array of PRRs causes macrophages to register a plethora of ligands as immunogenic. As for the recognition of bacterial infections, TLR4 may bind LPS to trigger an IFN response. Given that LPS is generally only found in bacteria, this allows for a clear-cut distinction between self and nonself. In contrast, all domains of life depend on nucleic acids to encode vital functions and constituents, necessitating a bias for nonself nucleic acid recognition to rein in the inflammatory response of macrophages. Even in health, billions of cells die every day, causing macrophages to continuously be exposed to endogenous nucleic acids.⁸⁶ These dying cells are generally scavenged to prevent the release of these immunogenic damage-associated molecular patterns, which may activate PRRs. The inability to clear nucleic acids or discriminate between self and nonself could otherwise provoke autoinflammation.^{87,88} To prevent these inflammatory conditions, modalities are in place to reliably call whether nucleic acids are of pathogenic origin (Fig 3). First, macrophages make this distinction on the basis of some basic characteristics of the nucleic acid ligand, including localization, conformation, and sequence motifs.⁸⁹ For example, macrophages minimize reactivity toward self-nucleic acids through spatial segregation. Several TLRs are located in endosomes, solely recognizing nucleic acids in the endosome lumen without reacting to self-nucleic acids in the cytosol, complementing the macrophage's implicit ability to endocytose and phagocytose.⁹⁰ However, MDA-5/RIG-I and cGAS are inherently responsive to dsRNA and dsDNA transcripts in the cytosol, inducing a potent IFN response on their activation.^{91,92} Safeguards are in place to limit the self-reactivity of these cytosolic sensors, such as MDA-5/RIG-I's greater binding affinity of viral 5'triphosphate ssRNA compared with endogenous capped ssRNA.⁹³

To further regulate the activity of the IFN system, macrophages depend on nucleic acid metabolism to alter the conformation and sequence of these ligands. First, 3-prime repair exonuclease 1 degrades endogenous ssDNA and dsDNA outside the nucleoplasm to prevent the activation of nucleic acid-sensitive PRRs, such as cGAS. Interestingly, macrophages feature a relatively high expression level of 3-prime repair exonuclease 1, possibly to prevent excessive activation of IFN pathways.⁹⁴ Second, macrophages use adenosine-to-inosine editing, entailing the posttranslational modification of RNA. On adenosine-to-inosine editing, RNA sequences will be destabilized, thereby preventing the activation of cytosolic nucleic acid receptors, diminishing IFN production.⁹⁵ This modification is facilitated by adenosine

deaminase acting on RNA 1 (ADAR1), a negative regulator of IFN responses.⁹⁶ Reduced RNA-editing was recently shown to positively correlate with IFN signatures in common interferonopathies, unveiling the importance of endogenous modulators in the IFN system.^{97,98} Mechanistically, ADAR1 also prevents activation of Z-DNA-binding protein 1, a central regulator of cell death and inflammation.⁹⁹ Three independent research groups recently showed that ADAR1 mutations cause Z-DNA-binding protein 1-mediated interferonopathy-like effects in mice.¹⁰⁰⁻¹⁰² Apart from editing endogenous transcripts, ADAR1 shows extensive editing capabilities in viral transcripts.¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁵ Third, sterile alpha motif HD domain 1 (SAMHD1) DNase depletes dNTP pools, to diminish reverse transcription. This mode of action makes SAMHD1 inherently antiviral because retroviral pathogens rely on reverse transcription for their integration into the host genome.¹⁰⁶ Furthermore, SAMHD1 interacts with nuclear factor- κ B and IRF7 to prevent their phosphorylation, thereby attenuating the inflammatory characteristics of macrophages. This effect is nicely depicted in SAMHD1-knockout macrophages displaying IFN signatures, even in absence of any further stimulation.¹⁰⁷ In essence, nucleic acid metabolism serves as a negative feedback mechanism to the IFN system by limiting the availability of immunogenic ligands.

Apart from containing IFN responses, there are mediators enhancing IFN responses. Because the IFN system is highly responsive to viral infections, suggested contributors to the efficacy of innate immune responses are endogenous retroviruses (ERVs), encoded in endogenous retroelements. These transposable elements are DNA sequences of retroviral origin, integrated into the human genome throughout history and evolution. Despite a staggering 8% of the genome being of ERV origin, these regions are generally silenced or lack functional open reading frames. Yet, some ERV elements are actively propagated to regulate immune responses.¹⁰⁸⁻¹¹⁰ In type II IFN-treated human macrophages, IRF1 and STAT1-binding ERV elements are enriched near ISG-encoding regions.¹¹¹ The transposition of ERV elements into immunomodulating regions of the genome suggests that macrophages could exploit previous retroviral exposures to expand their antiviral enhancer repertoire for future immunologic responses by providing transcription factor-binding motifs. More recently, macrophages were found to upregulate the expression of ERVs on stimulation with polyinosinic:polycytidylic acid (synthetic dsRNA mimicking viral RNA).¹¹² Here, the authors found knocking down one of the most strongly regulated ERVs to reduce antiviral activity of macrophages and in mice. Potentially, ERVs enhance IFN responses by increasing the availability of high-affinity viral transcripts and proteins to bind PRRs.¹¹³ These findings support an underappreciated regulatory role of ERVs in immunity.

Aberrant activation of macrophages underlies both local and systemic inflammation, through the presence of macrophage-lineage cells across distinct tissues. Specifically, the notable inflammatory potential of macrophages warrants the presence of regulatory mechanisms to harness their inflammatory potential. Coincidentally, failure to downregulate IFN-inducing pathways commonly associates with an inflammatory macrophage phenotype. In contrast, the IFN-producing potential of macrophages is extensive because they need to be dynamic in response to their environment. In accordance with their ability to regulate the expression of ERVs in response to a broad range of stimuli and

FIG 3. Regulators of IFN signaling in macrophages. Macrophages are commonly exposed to endogenous and viral immunogenic ligands. Host nucleic acid metabolism serves immunity and prevents excessive activation of cytosolic nucleic acid sensors by these ligands, restricting macrophage activation. Complementary to host nucleic acid metabolism, endogenous transcripts may heighten macrophage activation by providing immunogenic ligands. In addition, endogenous retroviral elements are suspected to contribute to IFN signaling by providing binding sites for transcription complexes ISGF3 and GAF near ISGs. *ERE*, Endogenous retroelement; *GAF*, IFN- γ activation factor; *MDA-5*, melanoma differentiation–associated gene 5; *STAT*, signal transducer and activator of transcription; *TREX1*, 2-prime repair exonuclease 1; *ZBP1*, Z-DNA-binding protein 1.

recognize distinct PAMPs,¹¹⁴ the regulation of ERV-mediated IFN signaling is critical in macrophages compared with other lineages.

THE IFN RESPONSE SIGNATURE IN MACROPHAGES

Macrophages convey immunity among others by monitoring their environment for potential threats to physiological integrity. On recognition of a threat, it is vital for macrophages to promptly get activated. Yet, aberrant macrophage activity induces and sustains unwarranted inflammation.¹¹⁴ In essence, macrophages are required to remain naive in health, yet potent in disease. Therefore, macrophages have evolved an intricate epigenetic program supporting their core functions and responsiveness.¹¹⁵ Epigenetic regulation entails the reciprocal addition and removal of marks onto the DNA or histones, and the differential expression of noncoding RNA. These epigenetic processes generally alter chromatin conformation, by either packing the nucleosome more tightly (heterochromatin) or loosely (euchromatin). The spatial configuration of heterochromatin reduces the accessibility of the DNA for transcription factor and transcription machinery binding, thereby decreasing transcription.¹¹⁶ Conversely, euchromatin features more open binding sites to augment transcription. This dichotomy is nicely illustrated when considering the rapid production of TNF by activated macrophages, in part explained by readily accessible TNF-encoding chromatin.¹¹⁷ Interestingly, epigenetic regulation extends beyond coding regions, affecting regulatory elements of the genome.¹¹⁸ Enhancers are distal regulatory elements able to loop toward distant promoters, binding

transcription factors to form an enhanceosome and collaboratively augmenting the transcription of genes.

Epigenetic landscapes are partially set during the process of cell differentiation, facilitating the phenotypical characteristics of the respective cell lineage. Consequently, macrophages show greater expression of ISGs than do B cells, T cells, and fibroblasts after type I IFN stimulation.¹¹⁹ Interestingly, the comparative analysis showed ubiquitously expressed ISGs to primarily be antiviral, whereas macrophage-specific ISGs encode for genes associated with pathogen sensing and innate immune signaling.¹²⁰ In addition, macrophages can be phenotypically polarized through the dynamic regulation of their epigenetic landscape by environmental exposures. On exposure to either type I or II IFNs, macrophages deposit active histone marks and reorganize their chromatin to enable an IFN response.¹²¹⁻¹²⁴ Type I IFNs support the inflammatory phenotype of the macrophage by enabling the open configuration of chromatin, marked by H3K4me3, at promoter regions of inflammatory genes.¹²⁵ Following type II IFN stimulation, macrophages show a large fraction of enhancers to be activated in absence of subsequent stimulation, with some of these enhancers found in long terminal repeat regions of ERVs.^{111,126,127} These effects are induced through the collaborative efforts of PU.1 and C/EBP with STAT1 and IRFs, supporting the recruitment of epigenetic enzymes.^{128,129} Often overlooked, type II IFN not only support the expression of inflammatory genes but also attenuate anti-inflammatory responses.¹³⁰ Epigenetically, type II IFN inactivates enhancer regions associated with anti-inflammatory responses, such as IL-10.^{128,131}

The chromatin-modulating effects of IFN may even extend beyond acute inflammatory responses and may have a significant

regulatory role in innate immunity phenomena like trained immunity. The ability to adapt or prime to pathogen exposures was once thought to be restricted to the adaptive arm of immunity. In more recent years, the innate adaptations to previous environmental exposures have been receiving increasingly more attention. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as trained immunity and is becoming a hallmark of innate immune responses.¹³² In line with trained immunity, increasingly more evidence points toward a memory role in inflammatory responsiveness after IFN exposures.¹³³⁻¹³⁶ Macrophages rapidly adapt to IFN exposures, by accelerating the recruitment of RNA polymerase II on exposure to a secondary stimulus.¹³⁷ How different environmental cues trigger distinct memory effects is of particular interest. As an example, endotoxins dose-dependently induce tolerance to subsequent stimulation in macrophages,¹³⁸ whereas some IFNs potentiate future macrophage responses.¹³⁷ Differential exposures can therefore induce specific memory or tolerance responses in macrophages. These findings support a unique immunomodulating role of IFNs in macrophages, extending beyond the canonical antiviral ISGs, which appear conserved among cell lineages.

DYSREGULATION OF IFNs IN INTERFERONOPATHIES

The term “interferonopathy” encompasses a broad range of inflammatory disorders driven by the dysregulated activity of the IFN system. Although interferonopathies are commonly suggested to be driven by type I IFN, type II IFN also contributes to the autoinflammatory processes as seen in SLE.¹³⁹ In macrophage activation syndrome, in particular type II IFN causes macrophages to be hyperinflammatory and release large quantities of inflammatory cytokines. In hyperinflammatory disease, the interplay between type I and II IFN signaling could be of particular interest,¹⁴⁰ because type I IFN has the potential to both amplify and attenuate the inflammatory phenotype of macrophages. The inflammatory consequences of interferonopathies commonly present themselves as dermatologic and neurological manifestations, but in time may compromise any physiological system.^{141,142} The pathological mechanisms of interferonopathies show commonality in the autoreactivity of the immune system against endogenous ligands, such as RNA and DNA transcripts. These transcripts convey their immunogenicity in an intracrine manner or enter the circulation as immune complexes (ICs).¹⁴³ These ICs are the product of plasma cell–derived autoantibodies reacting with endogenous antigens, such as RNA and DNA transcripts derived from apoptotic cells.¹⁴⁴ Monocytes and macrophages will recognize the presence of ICs, inducing an inflammatory phenotype contributing to autoinflammation hallmarked by IFN signatures.¹⁴⁵⁻¹⁴⁹ This places the macrophage at the forefront of interferonopathies, because they are professional tissue-resident phagocytes and show greater abundance in inflamed tissues. These inflammatory responses are inherently self-sustaining, because inflammation causes more apoptosis, accelerating disease progression. Interestingly, single-cell transcriptomics show monocytes of patients with SLE to already have an IFN signature, possibly potentiating the inflammatory activity of these cells before infiltrating the tissue to become macrophages.¹⁵⁰

Underlying the interferonopathies is the inability to down-regulate inflammatory responses and distinguish self from nonself. Interferonopathies are generally complex in origin,

because most cases are not triggered by a single genomic or environmental event, yet various mutations are known to be involved in their etiology. Often, loss-of-function mutations in mediators of IFN responses, such as 3-prime repair exonuclease 1, ADAR1, and SAMHD1, contribute to interferonopathy development.^{97,151} Likewise, gain-of-function mutations in components of the IFN signaling pathway, or enhanced ERV expression, may enhance the activity of these pathways.¹⁵²⁻¹⁵⁴ Collectively, these mutations augment the availability of highly immunogenic ligands to macrophages, prompting IFN responses. Outside of classic interferonopathies, IFNs bear significance to all sorts of inflammatory disorders. Merely the process of aging may trigger the innate immune system to induce chronic low-grade inflammation, which was recently coupled to the upregulated transcription of IRFs, IFNs, and ISGs.^{155,156} Similarly, IFN production, as seen in interferonopathies, associates with atherosclerosis progression.¹⁵⁷ IFN signatures in mouse plaque macrophages even appear to positively correlate with plaque severity.¹⁵⁸

The abundance of macrophages at inflammatory sites in classic interferonopathies and IFN-mediated inflammatory disease underline the key roles they play in pathogenesis. The common presence of immunogenic ligands at these sites is likely to activate macrophage IFN signaling, amplifying inflammation. In line with this, loss-of-function mutations linked to interferonopathies disproportionately affect macrophages. The expansive etiology and pathophysiology of IFN-driven autoinflammatory disorders warrant investigative efforts into all facets of the disease to support the development of novel therapies.

CONTEMPORARY TARGETING OF IFN SIGNALING

IFNs are appealing targets in combating infectious diseases because of their ability to regulate immune responses. Their involvement in the etiology of various inflammatory disorders also suggests that IFNs are a possible debility to health. Interferonopathies are a great burden to society, due to their significant prevalence and our inability to provide effective treatment to all patients.¹⁵⁹ Unfortunately, there is no clear singular cause of the IFN signatures observed in interferonopathies. Therefore, it is unlikely that a singular therapeutic will be effective in every patient. Therapeutic research will have to account for interpatient variability in the underlying cause of the IFN signature.

Contemporary therapeutics aiming to neutralize PRR ligands and IFNs, block IFN receptors, or attenuate IFN pathway activity are therefore under investigation. Given how genetic dispositions affect negative regulators of IFN responses associated with interferonopathies, therapies altering nucleic acid metabolism should be considered.¹⁶⁰ Because immune cells are highly responsive to circulating RNA, forming ICs, RNase RSLV-132 was developed to metabolize the RNA.¹⁶¹ Although the mode of action of RSLV-132 appears elusive, the drug appears to improve severe fatigue in patients suffering from primary Sjögren syndrome.¹⁶² Because monocytes in primary Sjögren syndrome appear to already show dysregulated IFN signaling, therapeutic targeting circulating factors may be of particular interest, especially because monocyte IFN-inducing pathways are highly responsive to nucleic acids.¹⁶³ Likewise, disabling the cell’s ability to recognize endogenous nucleic acids, by inhibiting PRRs, might be a viable therapeutic strategy. However, at this moment in time, no effective inhibitors for cytosolic PRRs have been described. The possibility of directly blocking type I IFNs was

realized by ronalizumab and sifalimumab, the latter being more successful in trials, yet both have not gone through phase III trials.^{164,165} Given their specificity for type I IFN subtypes, it leaves the ability of other IFNs to mediate immunity and possibly also autoimmunity. Anifrolumab is an mAb binding IFNAR to attenuate type I IFN signaling, substantially reducing the IFN signature and disease activity in patients with moderate to severe SLE.^{166,167} Alternatively, emapalumab, used for targeting type II IFN, is currently undergoing clinical trials for treating macrophage activation syndrome in patients with SLE.¹⁶⁸ Given how these trials are promising for patients with SLE, it will be interesting to see how these results would extend to other interferonopathies. JAK inhibitors, tofacitinib and baricitinib, have been approved for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, based on their ability to improve clinical outcomes by inhibiting the signaling pathways of JAK-STAT-signaling cytokines, which include all IFNs.¹⁶⁹ Also, in type I interferonopathies such as Aicardi-Goutières syndrome and stimulator of IFN genes-associated vasculopathy with onset in infancy, JAK inhibitors have shown promising results, underlining the importance of type I IFN in these diseases.^{170,171} The recently uncovered role of ERVs in innate immunity warrants investigation to better understand their contribution to macrophage phenotypes. Originally, ERVs are derived from retroviral pathogens not unlike HIV. The use of reverse transcriptase inhibitors, as used in patients with HIV, could prevent the formation of ERV-derived dsDNA and thereby lessen the activation of, for example, cGAS in myeloid cells.¹⁷² However, the effectiveness of reverse transcriptase inhibitors could be limited. cGAS is unlikely to be the only PRR sensing ERV-derived PAMPs. The ssRNA transcripts or even viral proteins could potentially be recognized by, for example, RIG-I/MDA5 or TLRs, respectively. In addition, enhancer-like functions are unlikely to be directly affected by reverse transcriptase inhibitors, apart from reducing the transposition of these ERVs across the genome. Depending on the immunomodulating mode of action of ERVs, pharmacological targeting of ERVs could reduce the burden of IFN-mediated inflammation. In contrast, IFN therapy could also hold promise as a treatment against infectious pathogens. The severity of viral respiratory infections, such as COVID-19, is negatively associated with IFN responses.⁴ These findings argue for the possibility of administering IFNs to support our defense against infections,^{173,174} and how inhibitory interventions could increase infection rates. On a similar note, immune responses can also be harnessed to target malignancies. The core homeostatic functions of macrophages, including promoting tissue repair and growth, may promote tumorigenesis.¹⁷⁵ By promoting a more inflammatory phenotype using IFNs, macrophages acquire greater antitumor activity.¹⁷⁶ To date, IFNs appear clinically relevant to the treatment of cancer.^{177,178} These are among the numerous ongoing clinical trials, and preclinical investigations, directly modulating the IFN system as a therapeutic strategy.¹⁷⁹ The contrasting pharmacological approach of either amplifying or reducing IFN signaling presents itself as a conundrum, a balancing act of appropriating inflammatory responses to the environment. Alternatively, targeting epigenetic processes has made its way to the clinic, able to effectively target various malignancies.¹⁸⁰ The scope of epigenetic targeting may hold merit outside of cancer and is receiving increasingly more attention in inflammatory disorders, such as atherosclerosis.¹⁸¹ Research has also shown there to be an epigenetic signature in systemic inflammatory disease, highlighting the potential

of epigenetic therapeutics.¹⁸² Although in its infancy, epigenetic targets modulating IFN responses are making an appearance in the literature and may prove to be therapeutic targets.^{129,183-185} For example, inhibition of histone deacetylase 3 was found to attenuate type I IFN production in macrophages, downregulating their inflammatory characteristics.¹⁸⁶ Recently, histone deacetylase 3 was found to regulate the antiviral IFN response of macrophages by controlling the expression of STAT1 and STAT2.¹⁸⁷ Similarly, bromodomain-containing protein 9 contributes to the remodeling of chromatin regions associated with ISGs, and its inhibition using small-molecule inhibitors reduces IFN signaling in macrophages.¹⁸⁸ These findings warrant further investigation of epigenetic targeting in inflammatory disorders. Furthermore, efforts should be made to assess how specific cell lineages manifest to hopefully contribute to our cellular understanding of these disorders. As macrophages are exposed to IFNs, they will be primed to partake in various inflammatory responses, which may heighten the severity of these autoimmune responses.^{37,125} Given their functional involvement in interferonopathies, targeting macrophages is likely to be an effective therapeutic strategy.¹⁸⁹⁻¹⁹¹ Furthermore, therapeutically targeting specific pathways in monocytes and macrophages could be an effective strategy as a more targeted approach to regulate IFN responses and inflammation.

MACROPHAGES: AT THE CENTER OF IFN SIGNALING

IFNs are key cytokines regulating cell homeostasis and cellular responses in both infectious and autoinflammatory diseases. Unlike most other cells, macrophages are at the center of IFN signaling because they are both important producers of IFNs in response to viral, bacterial, and self-antigens and sensitive responders to IFNs. Macrophages are complementary to the IFN system in every aspect: as a result of lineage-specific adaptations, IFNs uniquely affect macrophage phenotypes through long-lasting effects. Compared with other cell types, future advancements that generate novel targets and therapeutics within the IFN signaling pathways will have a disproportional impact on macrophage responses.

At sites of inflammation, macrophages can contribute to either resolution of inflammation or instead exacerbation and tissue damage by managing the inflammatory response. Yet, the importance of the macrophage to the IFN system is often overlooked as a driving force of autoinflammatory disorders, such as interferonopathies. The prominent effects of interferonopathy-associated mutations on the macrophage's phenotype indicate the importance of this cell in disease. We should therefore further extend the narrative of the macrophage as an orchestrator of IFN-driven inflammatory diseases. Balancing the IFN feedback loops in macrophages could be a promising therapeutic strategy for IFN-driven autoinflammatory diseases. A more detailed exploration of the pathways mediating IFN responses in macrophages will further advance our therapeutic understanding of inflammatory diseases.

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